

are planted; varieties such as IR36, IR42, IR50, and IR66, and some IR-based

varieties introduced via Vietnam (such as NN3) are also popular. To identify more

adapted varieties, IRRI-Cambodia Project trials were conducted in 13 provinces over four seasons 1989-90.

Table 1. Yield of 3 new varieties during 1989 and 1990 wet seasons in Cambodia.

Location	Field ^a (t/ha)							
	IR66		IR72		Kru		Check	
	1989	1990	1989	1990	1989	1990	1989	1990
Tonle Bati	-	5.1 ab	-	5.2 ab	-	5.7 a	-	4.8 bc
Por Lors	-	3.6 a	-	2.6 b	-	2.9 ab	-	2.9 ab
Ballang	4.8	3.8 ab	4.9	3.6 ac	5.2	2.5 be	4.1	4.0 a
Day Eth	2.7 be	5.1 bc	2.9 bd	4.7 bc	3.9 a	5.8 a	3.1 ab	4.8 c
Prey Kabas	3.6	3.6	1.8	3.2	2.9	3.2	1.8	2.9
Kbal Po	-	3.2 a	-	3.0 ab	-	3.2 ab	-	2.8 b
Chhbar Mom	5.4 ab	3.3	5.4 ac	3.2	5.3 ac	3.7	4.6 ae	2.5
Kompong Siem	-	2.5 bc	-	2.6 bc	-	3.0 a	-	2.7 b
Prey Khmer	5.4 ae	5.1 ab	5.0 be	4.9 ab	6.6 a	5.4 a	5.9 ac	4.9 ab
Toul Bakha	4.0 ab	3.5 a	4.2 a	3.3 a	4.1 ab	3.1 ab	3.2 bd	2.8 ac
Kirivong	-	4.2 b	-	3.6 bc	-	4.0 bc	-	4.2 b
Chumcar Daung	5.7 ad	5.2 ab	6.6 ab	5.4 ab	6.5 ab	5.2 a	5.7 ad	4.8 b
Slakou	-	2.0 ad	-	1.7 d	-	2.2 ab	-	1.9 bd
Kap Srau	-	4.7 ab	-	4.6 ad	-	4.0 cd	-	4.8 a
Prey Phdau	5.9 ab	4.5 ab	5.1 a	3.9 c	4.8 ac	5.1 a	4.1 be	4.6 ab
Ta Saang	2.1 ad	2.5 bc	2.7 ad	2.0 bd	2.3 be	2.7 a	2.7 ad	2.4 ac
Bek Chan	5.9	5.6 a	5.9	5.0 ac	6.8	5.2 ah	6.6	3.9 d
Tuk Will	2.3	2.0 ab	2.0	1.8 cd	2.3	2.1 a	1.7	1.6 d
Toul Lapao	-	1.5	-	1.3	-	1.3	-	1.3
Toul Chrem Chrom	-	1.9 ac	-	2.7 ab	-	1.5 bc	-	2.1 ac

^a Any two means having a common letter at a location in a year are not significantly different by DMRT.

Of 20 entries tested in 1989 and 10 in 1990, IR66, IR72, and IR13429-150-3-2-1-2 (named Kru) were best (Table 1). They yielded 4 t/ha across 13 locations during dry season 1990, against 3.2 t/ha of the highest yielding check. (IR36 and IR64 were the check varieties.) In 38 trials over four seasons and 2 yr, IR66, IR72, and Kru yielded 4.2, 4.1, and 4.4 t/ha, respectively, compared to 3.7 t/ha from the check. Other agronomic characters are given in Table 2.

These three varieties were tested in farmers' fields in 13 provinces, with a traditional early variety added as local check. At some of 75 locations, IR66, IR72, and Kru yielded more than 6 t/ha (average 2.5-2.8 t/ha). A few hundred tons of seed were multiplied by the farmers themselves during 1990. □

Table 2. Grain yield and ancillary characters of 3 early varieties in dry season (13 locations) and wet season (20 locations) trials in Cambodia, 1990.

Variety	Duration (d)		Plant height (cm)		Panicle length (cm)		Grains/panicle		Panicles/m ²		Yield (t/ha)		PAcp ^a	
	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet
IR66	106±1.3	110±0.8	75±2.5	85.8±1.5	21.3±0.10	22.8±0.4	89±8.4	101±6.0	329±15.0	286±15.7	4.0	3.9	3.2±0.6	2.07±0.42
IR72	115±1.2	114±0.8	72±2.5	81.8±1.9	21.9±0.46	21.7±0.4	85±9.5	86±4.1	306±18.6	292±15.8	4.0	3.6	2.0±0.8	2.21±0.40
KRU	112±1.0	113±0.8	75±2.6	83.0±1.9	22.9±0.46	21.4±0.3	88±11.0	90±5.34	373±23.0	317±17.5	4.1	3.9	2.7±0.7	2.14±0.34
Check	111±1.2	111±1.0	77±3.0	87.8±2.0	21.7±0.51	22.4±0.5	75±14.0	80±3.8	308±19.6	291±15.5	3.2	3.6	4.0±0.5	2.86±0.43

^aPAcp = phenotypic acceptability.

Integrated germplasm improvement—tidal wetland

Performance of short-duration rice varieties in tidal swamps of Indonesia

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We screened 23 promising lines to identify short-duration rice varieties that yielded well in sulfate acid soils at Unit Tatas substation, Central Kalimantan, 1987-88 (Table 1). Seedlings (21 d old) were transplanted at 25- x 25-cm spacing in 7.5-m² plots in a randomized block design with four replications. Fertilizer

Table 1. Some Chemical Characteristics of acid sulfate soils at Unit Tatas Substation, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia.

Characteristic	Depth	
	0-15 cm	>15 cm
pH H ₂ O	4.0	4.0
Organic C (%)	2.8	1.7
Total N (%)	0.4	0.2
P Bray (ppm)	1.7	1.3
K (meq/100 g)	0.2	0.1
Ca (meq/100 g)	0.4	0.3
Mg (meq/100g)	1.2	0.9
Na (meq/100 g)	0.2	0.3
CEC (meq/100 g)	22.0	37.0
Al (meq/100 g)	14.0	16.0
H (meq/100 g)	1.0	0.8
Texture (%)		
- Clay	37	45
- Silt	62	54
- Sand	1	1

was 90-60-50 kg NPK/ha. All the P and K, and half the N were applied basally at transplanting; the remaining N was applied 30 d after transplanting. Pest infestation was measured at peak incidence.

BW267-3 had the highest grain yield, followed by CR61-7039-236, IR6023-10-1-1, and IR19661-13-3-2 (Table 2). BW267-3 and IR6023-10-1-1 are intermediate tall, IR19661-13-3-2, and CR261-7039-236 are semidwarf. These four short-duration lines have the highest number of panicles/m² and can be developed for the tidal swamps. Grain of IR19661-13-3-2, IR6023-10-1-1, and BW267-3 are long, slender; those of

Table 2. Yield of 23 promising rice cultures at Unit Tatas Substation, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia, 1988.

Culture	Plant ht (cm)	Days to maturity	Panicles /m ²	Grain yield ^d (t/ha)
IR19661-13-3-2	104.7	130	214	5.1 b
BW267-3	118.2	120	232	6.7 a
IR6023-10-1-1	118.8	125	216	6.3a
CR261-7039-236	96.7	125	239	6.4 a
ROHYB15-WAr-3-3	125.8	145	201	2.9e
BW100	119.3	140	155	2.8 e
BR51-120-2	115.1	140	200	2.7 efg
CR1009	104.2	150	190	2.7 efg
IR9217-58-2-2	98.4	135	228	3.6 d
IR9217-6-2-2-2-3	108.5	135	205	3.6 d
Pankaj	106.9	145	196	4.4 c
IR13146-45-2	108.0	135	212	3.8 d
IR8192-31-2-1-2	101.1	140	147	2.4 fg
IR21586-R-31-1	110.4	145	198	2.4 fg
ITA230	102.7	140	217	4.4 c
IR14753-120-3	102.3	125	212	2.3 g
IR29723-88-2-3-3	100.4	140	179	2.3 g
IR33353-64-1-2-1	100.8	125	255	2.2 gh
IR19657-87-3-3	104.7	135	190	2.1 gh
IR4422-480-2-3-3	101.1	135	166	1.8 h
IR31917-31-3-2	95.6	140	171	2.4 fg
IR52	95.2	115	247	1.3 i
IR21836-90-3	107.7	140	208	1.1 i

^aValues followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

CR261-7039-236 are medium. Amylose content is 26-28%.

These four lines are resistant to leaf blast and stem borer. □

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Fertilizer management

Influence of organic and inorganic amendments, modified urea, and application methods on ammonia volatilization in saturated calcareous soil

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Ammonia volatilization from urea depends on such factors as rate of hydrolysis of urea, concentration of NH₄-N in the soil, and pH. Coating urea with some material can reduce NH₃ volatilization.

We measured NH₃-N volatilization from urea, neem cake-blended urea (NCBU), and neem oil-coated urea (NOCU) from a saturated calcareous soil (pH 8.25, 1.25% organic C, 23.7% CaCO₃, and CEC 19 meq/100 g soil) amended with gypsum, pyrite, rice straw, and rice husks. A forced draft chamber technique was used to trap ammonia.

Three-kg air-dried soil, equilibrated with soil amendments (20 t/ha) for 4 wk under saturated conditions, was placed in 5-liter wide-mouth glass bottles. N was applied at 150 kg/ha on the surface of the soil or mixed in the soil surface (see table for treatments).

The bottles were connected with an air compressor to flush out evolved NH₃ from the soil (4-5 liter/h). The NH₃ was trapped in 2% boric acid mixed with an indicator. Boric acid was titrated against 0.05 NH₂SO₄ at regular intervals for 30 d.

Application of soil amendments significantly reduced cumulative NH₃ volatilization. The reduction in NH₃ loss appears to be due to a lowering of soil pH on equilibration with soil amendments (see figure).

The formation of stable ammonium sulfate in soils amended with gypsum and pyrite may have contributed to reduction of NH₃ loss. Reduction of NH₃ volatilization from soil amended with rice husks and straw may be due to sorption of NH₄⁺ by organic matter.

NH₃ volatilization loss from soils amended with NOCU was lower because a thin layer of neem oil around the prilled urea acted as a physical barrier, reducing the rate of N release and thus the concen-

Mean cumulative N loss by ammonia volatilization in saturated soil, as influenced by soil amendment, source of N, and application method.

Soil amendment	Cumulative N loss (%)				
	N source			Application method	
	Urea	NCBU	NOCU	Surface applied	Surface mixed
Gypsum	11	11	4	11	6
Pyrite	10	7	4	8	6
Rice straw	12	12	5	13	6
Rice husk	13	13	5	13	7
Control	32	34	10	32	18
LSD (0.05)	Amendment x Source of N 2			Application method 3	

Soil pH on equilibration with amendments under saturated conditions.